

**TERMINOLOGY OF THE UZBEK LANGUAGE DURING THE
PERIOD OF INDEPENDENCE**

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During the years of independence, significant progress was made in the field of lexicology of the Uzbek language, especially lexicography. In particular, theoretical and practical research in the field of vocabulary is noteworthy. The creation of the five-volume "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language", several dozen small and medium-sized bilingual translation dictionaries, and more than a hundred monolingual, bilingual or multilingual terminological dictionaries during the years of independence indicates that special attention is being paid to the field of lexicography, and that interest in this field is growing. .

One of the great achievements of Uzbek linguistics and lexicography in the period of independence was the creation of the etymological dictionary of the Uzbek language. Although ED Polivanov wrote in the Short Uzbek-Russian dictionary published in 1926 that he had prepared an "Etymological dictionary of the Uzbek language" for publication, but this dictionary did not see the face of life. A lot of material on the etymology of the Uzbek language was given in Ayub Gulomov's doctoral dissertation (1955) on the topic "Problems of word formation of the Uzbek language", but it was also not published. The first etymological dictionary of the Uzbek language Sh. It was created and published by Rahmatullayev during the period of independence. The publication of this dictionary, consisting of three parts (Book 1: Uzbek words, 2000; Book 2: Arabic words, 2003; Book 3: Persian words, 2009), despite some defects and shortcomings in it, was a great event in the history of Uzbek lexicography.

After gaining independence, serious attention was paid to the fundamental reform of the education system in our republic. The adoption of the laws "On Education" and "National Program of Personnel Training" is proof of our opinion. Our president stressed that the textbooks and manuals left over from the authoritarian regime do not meet the requirements of the educational system, and made it an urgent task for our republic to create textbooks and manuals that meet the modern requirements.

It is known that in the world experience there are separate linguistic institutes or schools of literary studies, but there is no special institution that shares the achievements of national language and national literature as a whole with direct education. It is a clear fact that one cannot learn the mother tongue without national literature and national literature without the mother tongue in the decrees of the President, and the years of experience have confirmed it.

As a result of the admission of Uzbekistan to the United Nations as an independent country and the establishment of diplomatic relations based on the principle of equality with many countries of the world, the world community began to recognize the Uzbek language, our mother tongue, as the state language of Uzbekistan. Students who consider it an honor to speak Uzbek have created scientific centers for special study of this language in prestigious academic institutions of the world.

Before independence, Uzbek linguistics was mostly descriptive in nature, but in the years of independence, important theoretical problems of general linguistics were studied on the basis of the materials of Uzbek language. Our advanced linguists, who understood that it is impossible to create training manuals and textbooks that meet the requirements of the new era without fully and correctly solving the theoretical issues related to defining the essence of the language system and linguistic memories that occur in the process of its formation, focused on language units and lexical-syntactic phenomena related to them. focused on

justifying its theoretical aspects. As a result, M. Mirtojiev, A. Hojiyev, A. Nurmonov, N. Mahmudov, Y. Tojiyev, Sh. The works of such linguists as Safarov, A. Sobirov, and D. Lutfullayeva appeared."¹

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¹Hojiyev A. O'zbek tili morfologiyasi, morfemikasi va so'z yasalishining nazariy masalalari. – Toshkent, 2010; Nurmonov A, Mahmudov N, Akbarov A, Solixo'jayeva S.